

Critical Change Laboratories towards justice oriented transformations

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Abstract

This short paper presents an overview of the Critical Changelab model of democratic pedagogy, co-created by project partners in 10 different European countries. The aim of the model is to empower youth to take ownership of everyday democracy, fostering their involvement in direct actions aimed at promoting justice oriented transformations. While the project aims broadly at strengthening democracy in Europe, both the themes and issues explored by youth, and the methods used in the in different Change Laboratories link with current technologies. We offer an overview of the methods used in different Critical Change Laboratories, and offer a concrete example and initial experiences from a critical Change Laboratory, where Finnish youth explore the topics of polarization of society and marginalization of youth.

Keywords

ChangeLabs, democracy, youth

1. Introduction

Inspired by the call for the CHI community to consider what better than ‘good’ technology may look like, and to create a manifesto for the CHI community to support transformative technologies for children and youth, we present our work within the context of the Critical ChangeLab project. The primary goal of the Critical ChangeLab project is to enhance democracy in Europe by creating and implementing a flexible model of democratic pedagogy using a bottom-up approach that empowers youth to take ownership of everyday democracy, fostering their involvement in direct actions aimed at promoting justice-oriented transformations [15]. During the project, the ‘Critical Changelab Model of Democratic Pedagogy’ is co-created by project partners in 10 different European countries, following a participatory process with youth, educators, and other stakeholders, using Participatory Action Research (PAR) [11] and participatory evaluation [2]. The model has its foundations on the work of Engeström et al. [3,4], and is informed by a conceptual framework about criticality and relationality created during the project. Anyone can run a Critical Change Laboratory – It is intended for education environments, and thus it includes materials to help educators and facilitators design the labs.

While the project aims broadly at strengthening democracy in Europe, both the themes and issues explored by youth, and the methods used in the in different ChangeLabs link with current technologies. In the paper, we present the Critical ChangeLab process and methods, detail some initial experiences from Critical ChangeLab with Finnish youth and discuss our plans going forward.

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2. Critical ChangeLab model

Critical ChangeLab is a participatory, youth-centred, change-oriented process. Through this process, young individuals explore and challenge issues that create tensions in their daily lives, envisioning alternative paths toward preferred futures. Central to Critical ChangeLab is the reimagining of Western democracy, with young people leading democratic inquiries in partnership with stakeholders from education and civil society.

There are two versions of a Critical ChangeLab Model. The phases from the longer version of the Critical ChangeLab are merged to create a shorter version. The phases are illustrated in Figure 1 below.

PHASES [LONG]	PHASES [SHORT]	DESCRIPTION
0- ONBOARD	0- ONBOARD	Introducing the participants to the CCLAB and its context (democratic relations and democratic practices in everyday life) and discussing practicalities regarding the process.
1- QUESTION	1- QUESTION & ANALYSE	Questioning, criticizing or rejecting some Western democracy related values or practices related to young peoples' everyday lives.
2- ANALYSE		Analyzing the democratic relations of the current situation and their historic evolution .
3- ENVISION & EXAMINE	2- ENVISION & ACT	Constructing a model, activity etc. of a new idea that critically explores the problematic situation, and offers a solution, a way to influence or further investigating it.
4- ACT		Making meaningful changes in local environments.
5- REFLECT	3- REFLECT	Reflecting on and evaluating the Critical Change Lab process.

Figure 1: The phases of the Critical ChangeLab process.

During the process, the youth are introduced to the project, and practicalities related to the process. Next, they are invited to question and analyse some democracy related values or practices related to their everyday lives. In the next phases they explore the problematic situation and are encouraged to make meaningful changes in the local environment. Lastly, they reflect on and evaluate on the process.

3. Critical ChangeLab methods

The methods employed within Critical ChangeLabs are designed to facilitate participants' progression through the cycle of expansive learning [3], collectively identifying and resolving tensions and contradictions experienced within everyday democracy, empowering individuals to advance and evolve in their understanding and actions. The tensions always have roots, which are useful to detect, to better understand the present, and to vision the future activities. These tensions can stem from various sources such as the historical context of the school, shifts in the curriculum, demographic changes in the local community, and so forth. While some tensions may be rooted in broader societal or systemic issues, collaborative solutions, even minor adjustments to daily practices, can often be devised and implemented.

The methods used in Critical Change Labs are largely informed by project partners experience and expertise in e.g., critical pedagogy, arts and design, and activism. The methods can combine, for example: Futures thinking [6,16], Embodiment and performance [13,14], Narrative [1] and Making [8,9]. An important tool in the Critical Change

Laboratories are the Critical ChangeLab Boards, which consist in a set of canvases (paper-based or digital) where participants document evidence, ideas, as well as collective insights and alternatives. The methods in the Critical ChangeLabs aim e.g. at supporting criticality, encouraging questioning, and analysing values, norms and power relationships in own communities and on a societal level, considering alternative voices, building connections to diverse local community initiatives, fostering creativity and imagining futures, promoting open discussion and rigorous research, and overall encouraging participation in real life democratic processes and supporting the participants agency.

The methods used are linked with a variety of digital technologies, such as social media and gaming platforms, as well as prototypes that enable its deployment in various settings (face-to-face, hybrid, and virtual) using transmedia approaches. For instance, Scratch could be used to create speculative design games around democratic relations between humans, humans and technology, and humans and the environment.

The Critical ChangeLab partners are currently engaged in running the first Critical ChangeLabs PAR cycle in 10 different countries all over Europe with children and youth between the ages of 11-23. The themes the participants have chosen to explore in their Critical ChangeLabs include for example digital influence, climate emergencies, lack of cultural participation, democratization of education, migrant rights, identity and clothes, and social media and self-image.

4. Initial experiences with Finnish youth

We are currently engaged in running the first PAR cycle of Critical ChangeLab in a school in the Oulu area, with youth between the ages of 15-17. Here, the youth and their teacher go through the long version of the Critical ChangeLab, as they engage in the process as a part of their civics education at school.

After the initial meet-up with students to discuss the project and matters related to consent, we gathered together with the youth at the University for the **Question** phase of the project (Session 1). We started the session with Onboarding to set the stage for the coming sessions. Here the focus was to use such activities that would help in familiarizing the researchers, participants and the teacher. We started the session with a *mood mapping* activity [12] where all participants (including the researchers and teacher) were asked to close their eyes and think about how they feel before attending the first session of a Critical Change Lab. Participants were encouraged to use all their senses and also talk about their emotions. They were asked to write down any sensations, associations, ideas or emotions that they are starting with, and choose the most important ones. These emotions were then shared and discussed in the group, as we moved towards our second activity, co-creating a *code of conduct* for the duration of the project – A set of rules that promote any positive emotions and reduces the negative ones. Here the aim is to move towards cultivating activating positive emotions [7]. The code of conduct we collectively came up with included e.g. giving feedback actively, listening to what others have to say and respecting their opinions, creating informal relations between the adult actors and the youth, keeping the environment cozy and comfortable, and providing coffee for those early morning sessions. Figure 2 shows a participant discussing the results of the mood mapping, while creating the code of conduct for the group. The code of conduct is alive and new rules can be added on the go whenever the need arises, and it will help in creating the space safe and comfortable for everyone so that they can share their ideas without any discomfort.

Figure2: Creating the code of conduct during Phase 1.

After the mood and rules had been set, the youth and their teacher explored the question of what democracy related issues or tensions they would like to explore at the lab. Their initial ideas included e.g. the polarization of society, climate change, marginalization, bullying, and political decision making. The participants were each given two votes to give to the topics they were most interested in exploring, and thus they were able to narrow it down to two main topics- Polarization of society, and marginalization of youth which would be explored further in groups.

For the Question phase, we used *Mind-mapping* as an activity to examine more closely their chosen themes. They first created mind-maps to illustrate how the chosen issue is visible in their everyday lives and relations by looking at it from multiple perspectives and exploring different dimensions. The students had freedom to choose the mode for their mind-maps; one of the groups opted for a digital version while the other opted for the traditional paper and pen for their mind-map.

During **Analyse** phase (session) the participants moved towards mapping the actors [5] involved in the issue by focusing on who is or could be involved, in what ways these actors are involved, who are the merging actors and how the actors are connected to one another. These actor maps will provide a broader picture of the issue at hand while focusing not only on who is involved directly or indirectly and who is an emerging actor but also on who is meaningfully absent from the action.

Figure 3 below, illustrates participants creating a mind-map around the topic of marginalization of youth.

Figure3: Participants preparing a mind map around marginalization of youth.

In our next session centred around **Envisioning and examining** (Session 3) the youth will continue to work on their respective topics. We will start with an energizer “many uses” in which the participants are asked to look for alternate uses of everyday objects. The purpose here is to look at objects with an open mind to find new meanings, possible purposes and new opportunities. This would allow them to be creative and look for out of the box answers and help in warming up for the session. We will also use “Artifact from the Future” [10] as a method where participants envision futures they want to achieve, and the artifact is something belonging to those desired futures. It can be a postcard, or a letter sent by future generations as a thank you for the efforts of the present generation in bringing that future or it can be a headline of future newspaper that talks about how things are at that time.

During the **Act** phase (Session4), the students will visit the local FabLab where they will print the tokens of their envisioned futures on t-shirts or cotton bags. We will encourage them to bring their old t-shirts or bags to print on them to promote sustainable practices. These items with printed messages can be used as a conversation starter among individuals to share the idea of envisioned future(s) and how we should act to achieve it.

In addition to this quick feedback technique, in the final **Reflect** phase (session 5) we will reflect and co-evaluate the Critical Change Lab process with the participants by keeping the following guiding questions in mind; What was learned during each phase of the process? What were the impacts of actions taken and what future plans are there to keep making meaningful changes in the democratic practices? We will make zines; small booklets where one page is dedicated for each session and the participants can write, draw, or illustrate their views about each session by keeping the guiding question sin mind.

In addition, throughout the Critical Change Laboratories, the participants engage in reflection regarding what activities, methods etc are good enough to keep, what should be revised or thought over before reuse and what should be thrown away. We carry out this activity at the end of each session to get instant feedback from the participants regarding what they like or do not like and what should be improved for the coming sessions. The activity includes three separate boxes placed at a prominent place with the title “keep”, “rethink” and “throw away” written on them. The students are encouraged to give their

feedback and any other thoughts or suggestions they might have, so that the things could be made better not only for them in the coming sessions but also for the coming Labs. The responses for the activity are kept anonymous, so that the participants share their thoughts freely.

So far, we feel that the experiences for the youth and their teacher, as well as for us researchers have been positive. The only thing that the youth have hoped to “throw away” so far, have been early morning sessions warranting an early rise. As something for the researchers to “rethink” going forward, they have pointed out methodological details such as e.g. the various uses of post-it notes and mind maps, and allowing for more time for different tasks. As things to “keep”, they have mentioned mood mapping and linking it to creating the code of conduct, brainstorming together and having good conversations between the students and “everybody”. These initial experiences of using the Critical ChangeLab model for democratic pedagogy have been both inspiring and rewarding, and we look forward to continuing with this work.

5. Conclusions

This paper presented an overview of the Critical Changelab model of democratic pedagogy, co-created by project partners in 10 different European countries, consisting of 5 different phases (question, analyze, envision and examine, act, and reflect) The aim of the model is to empower youth to take ownership of everyday democracy, fostering their involvement in direct actions aimed at promoting justice-oriented transformations. We offered an overview of the methods used with youth in different Critical Change Laboratories, and presented a concrete example and initial experiences of a critical change laboratory, where Finnish youth explore the topics of polarization of society, and marginalization of youth.

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